

Conformational and Stereoelectronic Effects on the Oxidation of Unsubstituted and Alkyl-substituted 2,6-Diphenyl-4-piperidones with Peroxomonosulphate

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The versatility of 4-piperidones, the conformationally important group of compounds, has been reviewed¹. Despite a large number of oxidation kinetics of these compounds carried out with various oxidants^{2,3}, the mechanism of peroxomonosulphate (PMS) oxidation of 4-piperidones has not yet been established. The present study is focussed on the structure-reactivity correlation.

Results and Discussion

In the oxidation of 4-piperidones (Table 1) by PMS, good linear plots ($\gamma > 0.99$) of $\log [PMS]$ vs time and of k_1 vs $[piperidone]$ ($\gamma > 0.99$) passing through the origin have been obtained indicating the first order dependence on $[piperidone]$ and the absence of self-decomposition of PMS⁴. The change in the percentage of acetic acid in the aqueous acetic acid medium has no effect on the rate of oxidation showing no charge development in the transition state. The negative salt ($NaClO_4$) effect observed is suggestive of the nature of the reacting species, a dipole (piperidone) and the ion (HSO_3^-).

The activation parameters have been deduced from the rate constants determined at four temperatures (Table 1). The negative entropy of activation indicates a constrained transition state (epoxide) in the reaction path. The excellent linear Eyring plot indicates the operation of a unified mechanism in all substituted 4-piperidones.

Non-kinetic study: Absence of induced polymerisation

on the addition of methyl methacrylate to the oxygen-free reaction mixture rules out the possibility of a radical mechanism. The stoichiometry of the reaction, $[piperidone] : [PMS]$ is 1 : 2 for the piperidones 1-5 and 7-11 and 1 : 1 for 6 and 12 (Table 1). The main products obtained from the stoichiometric mixtures are α -diketones and α -ketols respectively characterised by tlc, ir and nmr spectral data and qualitative test⁵.

Substituent effect: In N-H series, the rates follow the order: 3,3-dimethyl > 3-methyl > 3-ethyl > 3-H > 3-isopropyl ~ 3,5-dimethyl while in N-CH₃ series, the order of reactivity is found to be 3-methyl > 3-ethyl > 3-H > 3-isopropyl > 3,3-dimethyl > 3,5-dimethyl (Table 1; Fig. 1). In general, the oxidation rates are faster in the case of N-CH₃ piperidones than in N-H piperidones with the exception of 3,3-dimethyl-2,6-Diphenyl-4-piperidone and its N-CH₃ derivative are shown to be anchored in a single chair conformation with the two phenyl groups occupying the least strained equatorial positions⁵. The alkyl group introduced in α -position to the carbonyl is also in the stable equatorial orientation⁶. However, the possible contribution of boat or twist conformation cannot be ruled out.

In N-CH₃ piperidones, the lone-pair electrons on nitrogen occupies the sterically more crowded axial position⁷. The 1,3-interaction between this lone-pair electron and the axial hydrogens at positions 3 and 5 could enhance the ground state energy of the reactant. This attributes to the

TABLE I—RATE AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS AT 50°

Compd. no	Substituent	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	AH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-AS^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	log A	AG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$10^2 k_s$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
1	2,6-Diphenyl-4-piperidone (P)	79.7	77.0	53.1	10.5	94.2	0.40
2	3-Me	71.7	69.1	67.7	9.7	90.9	1.34
3	3-Et	66.3	63.7	88.6	8.6	92.3	0.81
4	3-isoPr	71.3	68.6	80.4	9.1	94.6	0.34
5	3,3-diMe	43.9	41.2	53.7	5.2	90.9	1.37
6	3,5-diMe	76.6	73.9	64.1	9.9	94.6	0.34
7	1-Me (P)	72.0	69.3	70.6	9.6	92.1	0.88
8	3-Me	62.8	60.2	94.1	8.3	90.6	1.54
9	3-Et	53.9	51.3	122.8	6.9	90.9	1.35
10	3-isoPr	77.9	75.3	54.4	10.4	92.8	0.66
11	3,3-diMe	53.0	50.3	133.2	6.3	93.4	0.54
12	3,5-diMe	69.9	67.2	81.7	9.0	93.6	0.50

Fig. 1. Substituent effect at 50°

faster oxidation rates in the case of N-CH₃ piperidones than in N-H piperidones. The least reactivity in the case of 3,5-dimethyl is accounted by a large decrease in Me-OH interactions in the ground state resulting from a non-chair conformation⁸.

A simple explanation based on polar and steric effects of the alkyl substituents can support the relative reactivity of the piperidones. Methyl group in the 3-position being electron-releasing, enriches the electron density at the reaction site facilitating the epoxide formation in the rate-determining step and hence the enhanced rate. +I effect of ethyl group being greater it is expected to react faster than 3-methyl but the observed rates are found to be reversed. Simultaneous operation of steric and polar effects in 3-ethyl places it between 3-methyl and 3-H in the reactivity sequence. The bulky 3-isopropyl behaves as expected, the steric effect outweighing the polar effect.

In 3,3-dimethyl, one of the methyl groups should invariably occupy the axial position. Approach from the axial methyl side is sterically hindered and the reagent approaches from the less hindered side. The methyl group which is in the stereoelectronically favoured axial position helps in the release of electrons towards the reagent from the double bond. Hence 3,3-dimethyl is found to occupy the first place in the reactivity sequence in N-H series.

This also may be attributed to the steric relief in the product formation. The same is expected for 3,3-dimethyl in N-CH₃ series also. But it is found to be the last in the 3-alkyl piperidones of N-CH₃ series. Due to 1,3-interaction between axial methyl group and axial lone-pair electron in 1,3-trimethyl-2,6-diphenyl-4-piperidone, the chair conformation gets twisted⁹ and hence the reduced reactivity.

Mechanism : A mechanism involving an electrophilic attack of the oxidant on the -C=C-OH group is proposed to explain the observed results. Substantiated by the negative salt-effect and nil solvent effect, the rate-controlling step occurs between a dipole (enolic piperidone) and an ion (HSO₃⁻) under the experimental conditions resulting in a transition state without any further development of charge. The epoxide formed in the transition state by subsequent fast hydrolysis yields the first stage of oxidation product α-ketol. The resulting α-ketol undergoes further oxidation to give α-diketone for 3-H and 3-alkyl N-H and N-CH₃ piperidones. Steric overcrowding is mainly responsible for the limited oxidation to α-ketol in 3,5-dimethylpiperidone (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Rate law .

$$[\text{enol}] = \frac{k_1}{k_{-1}}[\text{P}]$$

Applying steady state approximation to epoxide-the activated complex

$$k_2[\text{enol}][\text{HSO}_5^-] = k_3[\text{Epoxide}]$$

$$[\text{Epoxide}] = \frac{k_2}{k_3} [\text{enol}] [\text{HSO}_5^-] = \frac{k_1 k_2}{k_{-1} k_3} [\text{P}][\text{HSO}_5^-]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d[\text{acylon}]}{dt} &= k_3[\text{Epoxide}] = \frac{k_1 k_2}{k_{-1}} [\text{P}][\text{HSO}_5^-] \\ &= K k_2 [\text{P}][\text{HSO}_5^-] = k[\text{P}][\text{HSO}_5^-] \end{aligned}$$

The linear Exner plot indicates the operation of single mechanism in all the substituted 4-piperidones.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. 4-Piperidones were prepared as per literature method¹⁰. The solutions of PMS and the piperidone were prepared in aqueous acetic acid. All the experiments were conducted in aqueous 75% (v/v) acetic acid medium under pseudo-first order conditions ($[\text{piperidone}] \gg [\text{PMS}]$) maintaining the ionic strength at 0.2 mol dm^{-3} by the adding NaClO_4 .

The kinetics of reaction were followed by monitoring the disappearance of PMS by iodometry at different intervals of time. The rate constants were computed by the method of least-squares. The reaction stoichiometry was

found out by taking a known excess of PMS over that of piperidone and allowing the reactions to go to completion (50°). The stoichiometry mixture was diluted, extracted with ether, ether layer dried (anhydrous Na_2SO_4), evaporated and the resulting product was characterised.

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